

Incentivizing, excluding, and enduring: On the complexities of quantitative research assessment in Lithuania

Eleonora Dagienė*, Vincent Larivière** and Ludo Waltman***

*eleonora.dagiene@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0043-3837>

CWTS, Leiden University, The Netherlands

Institute of Communication, Mykolas Romeris University, Lithuania

vincent.lariviere@umontreal.ca; *waltmanlr@cwts.leidenuniv.nl

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2733-0689>; *<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8249-1752>

Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada; *Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University, The Netherlands

Lithuanian research assessment prioritises Web of Science publications, aiming for international impact. This paper examines the policy, introduced in 2012, of excluding articles from journals with low impact factor or suspected artificial citation inflation. We analyse how this suspension policy affected domestic journals and researchers' behaviour. The results show that Lithuanian researchers' publications in foreign outlets increased, but concerns remain about the chosen outlets' quality and potential continuing manipulation of Web of Science metrics. These are initial findings of a broader study exploring policy dynamics and unexpected consequences.

1. Introduction

As a relatively small country with modest scientific resources, Lithuania aims to balance the pursuit of high-impact research with a diverse academic landscape. Starting in 2004, policymakers prioritised publications in journals indexed by the Web of Science (WoS), valuing its perceived quality assurance in the absence of established alternatives. This approach aimed to enhance the international visibility and impact of Lithuanian research. However, social sciences and humanities (SSH) researchers raised concerns about overreliance on quantitative metrics, arguing that these did not adequately capture the value of research in their fields and could potentially neglect their domestically published research.

This paper delves into the influence of indicators on research practices by analysing a specific quantitative research assessment policy: the exclusion, in research assessments, of articles published in WoS journals suspected of citation inflation or falling below a specific Journal Impact Factor (JIF) threshold. We examine this policy's origins and its effect on domestic journal publishing and researchers' publication behaviour.

By exploring the Lithuanian case, we aim to contribute to a nuanced understanding of SSH research evaluation practices, and of the potential unexpected consequences of introducing quantitative indicators.

2. Background: Lithuanian research assessment policies

Driven by global trends towards accountability in university research funding (Butler, 2003; Geuna & Martin, 2003) and the adoption of performance-based funding systems (Good et al., 2015; Hicks, 2012; Sivertsen, 2017; Zacharewicz et al., 2019), Lithuania established an annual research assessment system. This addressed concerns raised by the Research Council of Norway (1996) that 'too few research results are published in languages that allow

communication with international academic communities'. In response, Lithuanian policymakers prioritised internationalisation and adopted quantitative evaluation measures.

In the late 1990s, WoS became the primary source for benchmarking countries' research productivity (European Commission, 2001, 2007). During this period, scientometricians offered various WoS indicators for national research assessment (Luukkonen et al., 1993; Moed et al., 1995; Narin et al., 1991). Additional research based on WoS data explored the costs and benefits of collaboration (Katz & Martin, 1997) and journal internationalisation (Zitt & Bassecoulard, 1998). Despite coverage limitations and a bias toward English publications scientometricians deemed co-authored papers in WoS journals a strong indicator of international scientific linkages (Wagner et al., 2001).

Aware of that 'although many developing country scientists publish their research findings, most do so in journals of their own institutes or other local publications' (Wagner et al., 2001), Lithuanian policymakers embraced WoS papers in research evaluation for all disciplines, likely overlooking the platform's poor coverage of SSH literature (Hicks, 1999; Huang & Chang, 2008; Larivière et al., 2006). Thus, achieving 'higher internationalisation' and publishing 'more papers in the best international journals' remain ongoing goals for Lithuanian policymakers, driving the adoption of WoS metrics (Dagiene & Sandström, 2015; Maskeliūnas et al., 2015).

Throughout the performance-based funding regime (2005–2015), Lithuanian policymakers faced the same effects as many other countries. Quantitative institutional research assessment influenced individuals (Aagaard et al., 2015; Hughes & Bennett, 2013; Mouritzen & Opstrup, 2020; Rowlands & Wright, 2021), and had a range of unintended consequences (Dahler-Larsen, 2014; de Zwart, 2015; Elton, 2000; Franco-Santos & Otley, 2018). Notably, Estonian researchers evaluating research achievements in the three Baltic States (Allik, 2003; Lauk & Allik, 2018) pointed to Lithuania's creation of a 'cottage industry' of low-quality domestic journals, highlighting researchers' focus on quantity over quality in response to the performance-based system.

3. Methodology

Our mixed-methods approach combines policy analysis and bibliometric analysis. For the former, we obtained the annual research assessment regulations from 2004 to 2024 from the national register TAR (<https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/en/index>). These documents were analysed to understand the evolution of policies using indicators such as JIF and an additional policy of excluding journals based on low impact factor or suspected citation inflation. The journals whose articles were rejected, and for which institutions received no points for publications, were compiled into lists which we call 'lists of suspended journals'; these are accessible on the Research Council of Lithuania website along with the results of the annual formal assessments. Across the downloaded lists, we found 156 journals suspended from 2012 to 2019; most (109) appeared in the lists only once. Of these 156, 11 journals were indexed only in Scopus, leaving 145 WoS-indexed journals for further analysis.

The bibliometric analysis utilised the WoS database to track Lithuanian publications in the suspended journals. We used the in-house version of the database at Leiden University's Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS). The following WoS citation indexes were used: Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, Arts & Humanities Citation Index, and Emerging Sources Citation Index. We collected only articles and reviews with at least one author affiliated with a Lithuanian institution; four journals were

excluded from further analysis because they had no such items during suspension years. Finally, the JIF quartiles of 141 journals and their publishers at the time of suspension were collected from the Journal Citation Reports, WoS Clarivate. The analysis compared publication trends in suspended journals before and after suspension, aiming to assess potential changes in researchers' publication behaviour.

4. WoS indicators in Lithuanian quantitative research assessments

Policy analysis revealed salient shifts in Lithuania's use of quantitative metrics. When introduced in 2006, annual assessments determined nearly all state funding allocated to universities and research institutions. Initially, these determined nearly all state funding allocated to such institutions; since 2018, the assessments have been used to allocate 30–40% of state funding. Further analysis elucidates these assessments' impact on funding allocation and institutional strategies.

Assessments use separate lists of eligible outputs, with different initial output values for different disciplines remain the primary focus across lists. To calculate Funding Points (FP), formulas employ three main components: Initial Output Value (IOV), Fractional Institutional Share (of All Affiliations), and Journal Impact Indicators drawn from either WoS or Scopus depending on the field. The formulas have been revised over time, with the requirements for WoS papers playing a role in these changes (Maskeliūnas et al., 2015).

Notably, since 2010, for articles in the sciences, non-WoS journals are not eligible, and only WoS indicators such as JIF, Aggregate Impact Factor (AIF), and citations are employed in the impact metric components. However, for SSH articles both Scopus and WoS journal metrics have been used since 2015, with the inclusion of publications from non-indexed journals also permitted for evaluation.

Despite achieving their first JIFs around 2010 (with some even becoming top-ranked Q1 journals), Lithuanian journals remained largely domestic in 2008–2010 with 40–94% of articles authored by Lithuanian researchers (Dagiene & Sandström, 2015). Consequently, in 2007–2010, Lithuania still fell short of its internationalisation goals, with almost half of WoS publications originating from these Lithuanian-centric journals. Policymakers recognized this limitation: WoS indexing alone did not guarantee international collaboration. They responded by adjusting WoS indicator requirements year-by-year in subsequent regulations (Maskeliūnas et al., 2015).

While annual research assessments rely on quantitative metrics, a layer of qualitative evaluation exists, making it more akin to an informed peer-review process. The Research Council of Lithuania appoints expert panels composed of senior researchers. These experts work anonymously to avoid institutional pressure and assess submitted outputs for criteria beyond metrics, such as whether the outputs met the publisher or journal criteria for allowed outputs posed in regulations. To support their work, these experts are provided with readily available funding point values calculated using JIFs, AIFs, and citation thresholds. The Research Council collaborates with Clarivate to access these indicators, but the experts do not simply accept the pre-calculated scores. They have the authority to raise concerns during evaluation, especially if they suspect the points do not reflect the true quality of the research output.

According to legal acts issued by the Research Council, experts identified journals for suspension based on criteria aimed at curbing practices that artificially inflate JIFs. Initially

(2012–2014), these criteria included ‘high self-citation rates and (or) citations from low-impact journals’. After the 2015 assessment, the Research Council published a report (Pečiūra et al., 2016) clarifying two reasons for suspension: first, inflated citations, and second, low JIF (i.e., $JIF \leq 20\%$ of AIF of the subject category). According to this report, ten Lithuanian journals fell into the first category, and nine of these also appeared in the second category. The 2020 act establishes broader criteria for suspension: a 2019 self-citation rate exceeding 25% or a JIF, excluding self-citations, below 25% of category AIF.

Analysing these evolving requirements alongside changes in indicators of national journals reveals clear policy shifts. Moreover, researchers in Lithuanian mass-media expressed their concerns about Lithuanian editors gaming the system by artificially citing each other’s journals (Jackevičius, 2011; Lašas, Ainius, 2011a, 2011b).

5. Exploring suspended journals

Our dataset includes 141 WoS journals appearing at least once on the Research Council of Lithuania’s suspended journals lists (2012–2019) and having at least one Lithuanian publication during their suspension year(s). These lists were discontinued in 2020, as the experts chose not to compile them, coinciding with Clarivate’s new policy for title [suppressions](#) (Journal Citation Reports™ Reference Guide, 2023). However, the latest regulations have not abolished the journal suspension procedure, so experts could resume the compilation of such lists in the future.

The 141 suspended WoS journals vary by publishers and their locations. Springer Nature stood out with the largest number of journals (20) published in 11 countries: Russia (7), the USA (3), Ukraine (2), and others including Germany, Latvia, Iran, India, Belarus, Hungary, Netherlands, Poland, and Austria. Other well-established names such as Elsevier (6), Taylor & Francis (5), Wiley (4), and Emerald (4) also had journals suspended, with these originating from England, Taiwan, Russia, the Netherlands, Greece, the USA, Germany, and India. Overall, suspended journals originated from 34 countries, with Poland (21), USA (16), Russia (14), England (13), and Lithuania (13) having the largest shares.

These 141 journals published 2,968 Lithuanian articles and reviews during the period of interest 2,034 (68.5%) originated from 13 Lithuanian journals, and the remaining 935 (31.5%) were published in 128 foreign journals. Notably, 67 foreign journals had only one Lithuanian paper rejected from assessments, and 50 journals published 2–4. Only 11 journals issued 5 or more rejected Lithuanian papers. Figure 1 shows the breakdown of rejected articles (red) and those approved for funding (green) in these journals. The patterns vary considerably by journal: even though the *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal* was suspended seven times (2012–2018), it published five papers in 2019 (a non-suspension year) that received funding points. Conversely, *Acta Physica Polonica A* was suspended just once, with only one paper affected. The remaining 33 papers published in this journal during its non-suspension years received state funding. Notably, the mix of suspended and approved volumes for some journals indicates researchers continued to publish in certain suspended foreign journals.

Figure 1. The 11 foreign journals with five or more suspended Lithuanian articles. Red and green denote suspended and non-suspended volumes, respectively.

The same pattern holds true for 11 Lithuanian journals (see Figure 2), highlighting how a journal's suspension could change year-to-year. We excluded from this analysis two Lithuanian journals having no JIF in the years they were suspended (they were then Scopus-only). Across all journals, we found that a journal might not be suspended in one year (green bars) yet appear on the suspended list in subsequent years (red).

Only one Lithuanian journal, *Elektronika ir Elektrotechnika* published by Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), was suspended more than three times over the eight years the lists were compiled, having 230 articles in suspended volumes and 46 in non-suspension years. Two other journals published by KTU had fewer suspended articles (83) than approved ones (192). Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU) published five journals appearing on

the suspended journal lists, but only the *Baltic Journal of Road and Bridge Engineering* was suspended three times, with 41 suspended vs. 57 non-suspended papers.

Articles in Lithuanian journals not only were suspended most but were openly and harshly criticised in mass media. Čeburnis (2014) even voiced a desire to remove Lithuanian journals from the Lithuanian research assessment system on the grounds of low research value and institutional self-dealing.

Figure 2. Lithuanian journals by number of Lithuanian articles. Red and green denote suspended and non-suspended volumes, respectively.

6. Impact on domestic journal publishing

The compilation of suspended WoS journals coincided with the discovery of attempts to manipulate the research assessment system (Jackevičius, 2011; Lašas, Ainius, 2011a, 2011b).

Media reports revealed that some institutions inflated the standing of their own journals (Q1 or Q2) through self-publishing, self-citations, and citation cartels. Faced with public scandal, universities including KTU and VGTU admitted to manipulation and promised changes.

Some Lithuanian journals changed publishers, possibly in the hope of escaping evaluators' scrutiny and media criticism. For instance, VGTU co-published a dozen journals with Taylor & Francis in 2011–2017—even though, interestingly, Taylor & Francis did not refrain from publicly expressing concerns about the continuing self-citation explosion and citation cartels between VGTU and other Lithuanian universities (Čeburnis, 2014; Lašas, Ainius, 2013). Nevertheless, the VGTU journals co-published with Taylor & Francis were suspended only at the beginning of the suspension policy.

However, another VGTU journal, the *Baltic Journal of Road and Bridge Engineering*, independently published but implicated by policymakers in the VGTU journals cartel, was suspended three times in 2012 (then a Q1 journal), 2014 (Q3), and 2015 (Q4). In 2018, VGTU transferred its publishing to Riga Technical University, possibly in an attempt to escape the media criticism and fluctuations in national research assessments associated with the suspensions of VGTU journals.

Some Lithuanian universities sought collaboration with established international publishers to expand their journals' reach and potentially improve their JIF. A noteworthy example is the never-suspended journal *Medicina*, owned by the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences. *Medicina* started partnering with Elsevier several years after its inclusion in WoS, the journal received its first JIF in 2014, and in four years with Elsevier (2014–2018), its ranking improved from Q4 to Q3. A subsequent partnership with MDPI further boosted its JIF (Q2 in 2020) and publication numbers (from 109 articles in 2018 to 1840 in 2022, according to Journal Citation Reports).

These findings suggest that for institutions and researchers, the suspension policy is akin to a lottery: funding points depend on the panel experts' decisions, which lack clear consistency.

7. Impact on researchers' publishing behaviour

The inconsistency in journal suspensions, with publications accepted one year only to be suspended the next, may have distanced researchers from Lithuanian journals. Figure 3, providing the total number of articles and reviews published in domestic and foreign WoS journals from 2005 to 2022, might be interpreted as evidence that Lithuanian science policymakers achieved their goal. Following the implementation of the suspension policy in 2012, the percentage of domestically published papers dropped from 51.6% to 38.1%, then even further to only 11.6% in 2019, when the compilation of suspended journal lists ceased. In 2019, an impressive 88.4% of papers were published abroad.

As the bibliometric analysis shows, in 2022, Lithuanian researchers published with domestic publishers only 7.8% of their WoS papers; Springer and Elsevier journals published 8.3% and 13.6%, respectively, of all Lithuanian papers. The absolute leader was MDPI with 30.9%, which is quite close to the 39.3% of the remaining 1,330 publishers. However, further exploration is needed to determine whether these foreign journals are demonstrably better than Lithuanian journals (and are not purely domestic or institutional in another country) and whether this suspension policy has truly contributed to a more internationalised Lithuanian science landscape.

Figure 3. Top publishers of Lithuanian outputs, 2005–2022, WoS (SCIE, SSCI, A&HCI, ESCI).

8. Discussion, initial conclusions, and further research

In this paper, we examined the complexities of quantitative research assessment in Lithuania—namely, how the suspension policy emerged and how it affected researchers’ publication behaviour and domestic journal publishing.

Policy analysis and bibliometric analysis revealed that Lithuania focused on WoS indicators with the intent of integrating Lithuanian scholarship into the global research landscape. These efforts resulted in a proliferation of domestic journals publishing a high proportion of Lithuanian outputs. The evolving regulations demonstrate a continuous effort to balance quantitative metrics with qualitative evaluation. Still, concerns remain about the fairness of a system heavily reliant on WoS indicators.

The analysis of suspended journals highlights the challenges of maintaining quality control. The suspension data reveals a mix of compliance and continued publishing in suspended journals, suggesting both a deterrent effect and a need for further action.

Lithuania’s focus on WoS indicators incentivized publishing in top journals but also created an opening for institutional manipulation. The research assessment system’s reliance on local expert panels and unclear suspension criteria created uncertainty for researchers who were incentivized to publish in Q1 or Q2 journals. Inconsistencies in evaluation outcomes ultimately strained the relationship between researchers and domestic journals, leading to a decline in their use.

While the Lithuanian research assessment policy achieved its goal of increasing foreign publications, this shift raises concerns about the quality of the chosen outlets. Further

investigation is needed to determine whether the internationalisation of Lithuanian research comes at the cost of rigour, whether manipulation tactics have simply shifted to the global stage, and if so, whether Lithuanian policymakers are aware of these practices.

Meanwhile, although the number of Lithuanian papers in domestic journals declined, domestic journals have persevered. Lithuanian universities and research institutions still publish around 200 peer-reviewed journals, mainly small diamond open access periodicals (Grigas et al., 2021). Further research could study what role the Lithuanian journals play in institutional research and their potential for collaboration and shared services in the global landscape of diamond open access journals (Bosman et al., 2021).

Finally, empirical evidence presented in this study can be used for further exploration of the policy dynamics between the state, scientific elites, and research organisations (Chou et al., 2017; Whitley & Gläser, 2014) and studies on unintended consequences (Dahler-Larsen, 2014; de Zwart, 2015; Franco-Santos & Otley, 2018).

Open science practices

This paper is based on two types of data – Lithuanian research assessment policies and metadata of articles authored by Lithuanian researchers obtained from Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science. Due to license restrictions, Web of Science data cannot be made openly available. The Lithuanian research assessment policies are freely available in the Register of Legal Acts managed by the Office of the Seimas of the Republic of Lithuania (see <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/en/index>).

Author contributions

ED: investigation, visualisation, writing – original draft; VL: supervision, writing – review & editing; LW: supervision, writing – review & editing.

Competing interests

Authors have no competing interests to declare.

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